

The Influence of Servant Leadership and Work Environment on Employee Performance

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ABSTRACT: This research has three variables, namely servant leadership (x1), work environment (x2) and employee performance (y) which aims to determine servant leadership, work environment and employee performance at the women's and children's empowerment service in Bandung City. The method used in this research is quantitative with a descriptive and verification approach. Primary data collection techniques were obtained through questionnaires, observation and interviews. Secondary data was obtained through libraries and reviewed documents. The population of this study was 100 employees at the Bandung City Women's and Children's Empowerment Service. The magnitude of the influence of servant leadership and the work environment on employee performance was used by multiple linear regression analysis or path analysis and determinant coefficients with the help of SPSS for window 24. The results of the discussion of servant leadership and the work environment on employee performance at the Bandung city women's and children's empowerment service and the results of respondents'answers From the questionnaire it turns out that servant leadership and the work environment on employee performance at the Bandung City Women's and Children's Empowerment Service, servant leadership and the work environment as a whole show a positive and good response. It can be concluded that there is a fairly strong influence between servant leadership and the work environment on employee performance and other factors.

KEYWORDS: servant leadership, work environment, employee performance

RESEARCH BACKGROUND

Human Resources are the main component of an organization who are active planners and actors in every organizational activity. They have heterogeneous thoughts, feelings, desires, educational status and background, age, gender which are brought into an organization so that unlike machines, money and materials, which are passive in nature, can be mastered, can be controlled and can be fully regulated in supporting the achievement organization goals.

The organization is also a management tool that shows clear duties, obligations and roles for its personnel. Humans as individuals have diverse traits and characteristics. The strength of human resources is formed by the different traits and characteristics of each individual, which are united and expressed in a unified view manifested by the leader. There are three classifications contained in an organization, namely the first, there are those who lead; secondly, there are several people who must be led in an organization's management to achieve goals, and the last is how to implement communication and efforts to build good relationships with users.

Human resources are the resources that manage and control all elements in the organization. Therefore, the performance of an organization cannot be separated from the role of its people as the most important element in managing and controlling the progress and decline of an organization. Thus, human resource management needs to strive for techniques and strategies to improve employee work performance, which will directly contribute to work results and organizational effectiveness, so that organizational goals will be achieved. To obtain quality human resources, human resource management is needed, which is an inseparable part of management in general, namely it is the main key in achieving organizational goals.

In managing an organization, it is necessary to pay attention to the needs of individual characteristics in providing encouragement to these individuals so that they have optimal performance, which will ultimately influence the success of the organization/agency as a whole. For this reason, a commitment to work is needed to realize the goals and objectives of the organization.

Human resource management is the policy and practice of determining human aspects or human resources in management positions, including recruiting, screening, training, rewarding and evaluating (Sedamaryanti, 2017). The goal of human resource management in general is to ensure that organizations are able to achieve success through people. The human resource management system can be a source of organizational capability that allows companies or organizations to learn and use opportunities for new opportunities (Sedamaryanti, 2017).

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Based on the results of observations at the Bandung City Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Service, it can be seen that employees work not impulsively or purposefully. They work alone in a haphazard way of working, lacking direction, chaotic, and management functions almost do not apply, work discipline is low. Many working hours are not effective in relation to their work duties. Attitudes to work concisely, neatly, well cared for, diligently and so on are not satisfactory. Apart from that, there is no awareness that work success is rooted in the values one has and habitual behavior.

Servant leadership according to Northouse (2013) is an approach that pays attention to the problems of their followers, empathizes with them, and develops them. According to Sendjaya (2015, p.7), in contrast servant leaders view themselves as servants (stewards), the word steward comes from the word 'oikonomia' which means house manager. Just as a house manager is entrusted with the responsibility of managing business affairs in the household. As a natural expression of servanthood behavior in a servant leader, he tries to be responsible not only for the people he serves but also for other people (Sendjaya, 2015, p.32)

The employee's work environment is a determining factor in the process of carrying out tasks in order to achieve the goals and objectives of the organization. The work environment in the company also influences the performance carried out by employees. (Mangkunegara, 2017) states that: "The achievement motive that employees need to have must be developed from within themselves apart from the work environment. This is because the achievement motive that is grown from within oneself will form a personal strength and if the work environment situation also supports it, achieving performance will be easier." The work environment itself consists of physical and non-physical elements that are attached to it.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND EMPIRICAL STUDIES

Servant Leadership

Khan, Muhammad Mumtaz; Muhammad Shujaat Mubarak (2022) said that servant leadership has been proven to increase learning, job satisfaction and work ability. Likewise, servant leadership has become a source for improving employee performance, creativity and innovative work behavior.

Huning, Tobias M; Hurt, Kevin J; Frieder, Rachel E (2020) said that a servant leader is a servant first who begins with a natural feeling that someone wants to serve to serve first. Then the conscious choice gives rise to the ideals to dream. The best, and difficult test to administer is whether those served grow as individuals, whether they, when served, become healthier, wiser, freer, more independent and more likely to become servants and, what impact this has on the most disadvantaged groups of society. , will they benefit, or at least not be harmed any more.

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1. Altruistic calling Altruistic is a voluntary act to help others without expecting anything in return. Servant leadership describes existing work as service to the group and people served, service itself is a reward for a servant leader.
2. Emotional healing When people feel disappointment with work performed, can influence future commitment to the organization. With the commitment of a servant leadership in facilitating the emotional healing needed to increase the morale of subordinates from the feelings of disappointment experienced, they can move forward and develop together in achieving organizational goals.
3. Wisdom the ability to see what is desired in a situation now and provide solutions on how to achieve it. Servant leadership has wisdom and empowers it in the people around them.
4. Persuasive mapping Leaders influence the people around them not through formal position, but through personal abilities in persuasion. Persuasive mapping helps other people see the big picture and find ways to achieve goals.
5. Organizational stewardship, servant leadership as administrator Long-term thinking and planning organizations describe the extent to which leaders prepare the organization to make positive contributions to its environment, such as through community service and community development programs as well as encouraging higher education.

Work environment

Several experts define the work environment as follows: According to Semito (2000), the work environment is defined as everything around workers that can influence them in carrying out their assigned tasks.

Furthermore, according to Sedarmayati (2017) defines the work environment: "The work environment is the totality of tools and materials encountered, the surrounding environment in which a person works, work methods, and work arrangements both as an individual and as a group."

The work environment has several definitions put forward by several experts, including according to which the formation of a work

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environment related to human abilities and work productivity is influenced by physical, chemical, biological, physiological, mental and socio- economic factors.

From the opinions above, it can be concluded that the work environment is everything around an employee while working, whether physical or non-physical, directly or indirectly, which can affect him and his work while working. Work environment is the working conditions felt by employees while working, both in the form of physical and non-physical environments (Sedarmayanti, 2017).

Performance

Nazir, Owais; Islam, Jamid Ul. (2017) said that performance management as a management tool is important for maintaining harmony and instilling organizational progress. Better employee performance management is important for improving organizational performance and effectiveness. Employee engagement improves employee performance. Engaged employees demonstrate a variety of productive behaviors that enhance synergistic team efforts towards organizational goals and these synergistic efforts lead to improved employee performance. The reason behind this effort and performance is the ability of the employees involved to transfer their tasks throughout an organization when workers react to goals as a group, their productivity increases. Performance is defined as the achievement of a goal, achieving a goal is a requirement to produce performance that has been determined both in terms of quality and quantity of achievement using the abilities possessed. Meanwhile, the definition of performance itself cannot be separated from what has happened in work activities, both in the office and outside the office. What employees experience in the improvement process and their abilities at work will obtain balanced results. This experience is influenced by several factors such as: the quality of employee performance and employee characteristics which are a reflection of employee professionalism.

Many experts have different opinions regarding the definition of performance. This happens because there are differences in the background and views of each expert regarding the word performance. Even in terms of terminology itself, there are many terms that are always used apart from performance, also for work, work results and works as well as work achievements.

Liang, H., Wang, N., Xue, Y. and Ge, S. (2017), said that performance has good durability so it can be a solution that needs to be updated. Prasetya Irawan (1995), said that performance is the result of a worker's work in a management process or organization as a whole, where the results of this work must be shown in concrete evidence and can be measured or compared with predetermined standards.

As is understood, an organization is a social unit of groups of people who interact with each other based on certain patterns in an effort to achieve specified goals. In other words, an organization is not just a collection of people and not just a division of work, but within the organization there is employee engagement and mutual influence. Hani Handoko (2014) stated that the essence of an organization is people whose efforts must be coordinated, composed of a subsystem that is interconnected and dependent, collaborates on the basis of division of work, roles and authority and has certain goals to be achieved. To achieve organizational goals well and optimally, basic and systematic engineering is needed by utilizing the people in the organization. This basic and systematic engineering is what is known as management.

Basic personnel management techniques can affect a company's bottom line. The management techniques applied by these leaders have a big impact on productivity and work performance. Performance appraisal is an organizational process in assessing the performance of its employees. The purpose of performance appraisal in general is to provide feedback to employees in an effort to improve their performance so as to improve overall organizational performance, and is specifically carried out in relation to various policies towards employees such as promotions, salary increases, training and so on, so that the assessment Performance can be a basis for assessing the extent to which HRM activities such as recruitment, selection, placement and training can be carried out well and directed. Performance dimensions according to (Bangun, 2012) assess work results and assess behavior.

Based on this, generally there are similar views regarding various human needs that can be identified. These various needs can become a motive or encouragement for the person concerned to carry out activities or do something,

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Fig 1. State of the art

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this research is the survey method. The survey method is research that takes samples from the population and uses questionnaires as the main data collection tool (Singarimbun and Efendi, Ed, 2005).

The study objective of this research is verification. Where in this research, verification research aims to determine the influence of servant leadership, work environment, on employee performance. Remembering that this research is causal correlational research, namely research to determine the level of relationship between two or more variables, without making changes, additions or manipulation to existing data (Arikunto, 2010:4). The type of investigation in this research is causality, which is a type of research that states that there is a causal relationship between independent and dependent variables, in this case the influence of servant leadership and the work environment as independent variables on the dependent variable, namely employee performance at the Bandung City Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Service. . The time horizon in this research is cross-sectional, that is, information from sample respondents is collected directly from the research location empirically with the aim of knowing the opinions of respondents regarding the object under study. In this research, data sources that can provide information on the main problem consist of primary data and secondary data. Primary data is data obtained directly from the source, namely the research analysis unit, through interviews, questionnaires and observations. Meanwhile, secondary data is data obtained indirectly from the analysis unit, from certain sources through reviewing available documents or reports descriptively through observations while the researcher worked at the Bandung City Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Service where the object of research was. Researchers in conducting this research took the population as all employees at the Bandung City Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Service, totaling 100 employees. The sampling technique for this research was carried out using the Probability Sampling technique, sampling in this research used random samples (Random Sampling). Meanwhile, the sampling technique used a formulation from Taro Yamane or Slovin (in Riduwan 2005:65) for 44 employees. As well as information implemented through path analysis.

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DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

Result of Validity Test of Servant Leadership Variable Instrument

Item	Corrected Item – Total Correlatoin	Nilai r – Tabel	Kategori
X1-1	0,456	0,30	Valid
X1-2	0,505	0,30	Valid
X1-3	0,395	0,30	Valid
X1-4	0,538	0,30	Valid
X1-5	0,656	0,30	Valid
X1-6	0,491	0,30	Valid
X1-7	0,446	0,30	Valid
X1-8	0,462	0,30	Valid
X1-9	0,595	0,30	Valid
X1-10	0,507	0,30	Valid

Source: Primary data reprocessed

The statements in the Servant Leadership variable instrument above consist of 10 items. The test results for this variable meet the required criteria, namely > 0.30 , and it is concluded that statement items 1 to 10 are declared valid as indicators of Servant Leadership. Results of Validity Test of Work Environment Variable Instruments

Item	Corrected Item – Total Correlatoin	Nilai r – Table	Kategori
X2.1	0.465	0,30	Valid
X2.2	0.571	0,30	Valid
X2.3	0.672	0,30	Valid
X2.4	0.468	0,30	Valid

Source: Primary data reprocessed

The statement in the work environment variable instrument above consists of 4 items. The test results for this variable meet the required criteria, namely > 0.30 . Thus it can be concluded that statement items 1 to 4 can be declared valid and truly as indicators of the Work Environment.

Result of Validity Test of Employee Performance Variable Instrument

Item	Skor	Kategori
Y.1	0.375	Valid
Y.2	0.399	Valid
Y.3	0.432	Valid
Y.4	0.331	Valid

Source: Primary data reprocessed

The statement in the Employee Performance variable instrument above consists of 4 items. The test results for this variable meet the required criteria, namely > 0.30 . Thus it can be concluded that statement items 1 to 4 can be declared valid and truly as indicators of Employee Performance.

Reliability Test Results Category Score Variables

No.	Variabel	Skor	Kategori
1.	Servant Leadership (X1)	0.894	Reliabel
2.	Work Environment (X2)	0.893	Reliabel
3.	Employee Performance (Y)	0.872	Reliabel

Source: Primary data reprocessed

The results of the reliability test above can be stated that all variables are in the reliable category, because the score is > 0.60 . In this way, the research instrument used for each variable in this study can be declared reliable and truly a reliable measuring instrument and has a high level of stability, in the sense that if the measuring instrument is carried out repeatedly, the results of testing the instrument will show results. which is fixed.

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Recap of the Servant Leadership Variables Scores

SERVANT LEADERSHIP VARIABLES			
NO	STATEMENT	SCORING	category
1	Every leader must be able to help his subordinates	175	well
2	Each leader helps without strings attached	150	enough
3	Every leader is expected to display accuracy	180	good
4	Every leader is expected to make analysis	179	good
5	Every leader is expected to focus on the process	185	well
6	Every leader is expected to focus on good results	178	well
7	Every leader is expected to have sufficient goals	149	enough
8	Every leader is expected to have 155 sufficient goals	155	enough
9	Every leader can work 180% together	180	well
10	Every leader can organize 181 well	181	well

Source: Primary data reprocessed

Recap of Work Environment Variable Scores

WORK ENVIRONMENT VARIABLES			
NO	STATEMENT	SCORING	Category
1	Every employee has work equipment	175	good
2	Every employee receives a working atmosphere	185	good
3	Every employee has a good relationship	145	enough
4	Every employee has the opportunity to progress	149	sufficiently

Source: Primary data reprocessed

Recap of Employee Performance Variable Scores

EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE VARIABLES			
NO	STATEMENT	SCORING	Category
1	Every employee has an appropriate work quantity of	180	good
2	Every employee has good work quality	145	sufficiently
3	Every employee has sufficient initiative in working	146	sufficiently
4	Every employee is able to work independently	175	well

Source: Primary data reprocessed

Calculation Results of the Effect of Servant Leadership (X1), Work Environment (X2), on Employee Performance (Y) simultaneously.

Model Summary

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.927 ^a	.859	.858	1.97647

a. Predictors: (Constant), Servant Leadership, Work_Environment

b. Dependent Variable: Employee_Performance.

ANOVA

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	2934.677	3	978.226	250.415	.000 ^b
1 Residual	484.396	124	3.906		
Total	3419.074	127			

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a. Dependent Variable: Employee_Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Servant Leadership, Work_Environment

Calculation Results of the Effect of Servant Leadership (X1), Work Environment (X2), on Employee Performance (Y) partially.

Coefficients^a

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Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	.521	1.138		.458	.648		
Servant Leadership	.175	.038	.249	4.627	.000	.395	2.533
Work environment	.466	.063	.533	7.406	.000	.221	4.535

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

CONCLUSION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATION

Based on the results of the research and discussion regarding the influence of Servant Leadership and the Work Environment on Employee Performance in the Bandung City Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Service, the author can draw the conclusion that Servant Leadership in the Bandung City Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Service is in the good category. This can be said. It is seen that every leader is expected to focus on processes that are classified as good. The work environment at the Bandung City Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Service is in the good category. This can be seen that every employee receives a work atmosphere that shows a good environment. Employee performance at the Bandung City Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Service is in the good category. This is intended to mean that each employee has the appropriate quantity of work in the good category. Suggestions for the Bandung City Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Agency: Servant Leadership is one of the important factors that must be considered to increase work effectiveness, the ability to work under pressure needs to be improved, in a way that every leader is expected to have a goal in completing a job, Work Environment, overall In general, it is good, but the aspect that every employee must have good relationships and the performance of employees at the Bandung City Women's Empowerment and Child Protection Service needs to be improved, especially in terms of good work quality. There is further research using independent variables other than servant leadership and work environment.

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